

Between Vision and Structure: Pre-Service Teachers' Constructions of Cooperative Learning as a Vehicle for Citizenship Education in Pakistan

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Abstract: *In Pakistan, citizenship education in elementary schools primarily uses the transmission model of teaching, in which students are denied opportunities to acquire the civic competency to participate in the democratic system of the country. This paper reports a qualitative study on how pre-service teachers in a Pakistani university construct their understanding of cooperative learning as an approach to teaching citizenship education. Data were gathered using semi-structured interviews with ten final-year BS Education students, having one or more practicum placements, analysed through Reflexive Thematic Analysis. The analysis yielded four themes: cooperative learning as a civic and social formation process; active teacher facilitation is key to effective implementation and is non-negotiable; systemic barriers limit implementation in public schools; and conditional professional readiness is influenced by the short duration of practicum placements. The authors suggest that the participants have conceptual and motivational resources but lack structural support; they lack the support to enact these resources. The key finding is that the problem of cooperative learning implementation is not only pedagogical but also structural and policy in nature and, therefore, has clear policy and teacher education programme design implications for educational policy in Pakistan.*

Keywords: Cooperative Learning, Citizenship Education, Pre-Service Teachers, Teacher Education in Pakistan, Reflexive Thematic Analysis, Practicum, Social Interdependence Theory

Introduction

Citizenship education has become increasingly relevant internationally because of increasing pressures on democratic institutions and processes, civic disaffection, and civic education

inequalities, all of which are driven by growing social polarisation (Westheimer & Kahne, 2004). This is both a theoretical and practical issue at the elementary level, as elementary dispositions are often linked to civic behaviours in adulthood. This is relevant to Pakistan because the majority of the pedagogy observed in the elementary classrooms is of a transmission type; the learners are passive recipients of information and not yet active members of a civic community. Cooperative learning in this context has shown potential for developing these active, relational, and participative abilities needed for citizenship education (Johnson & Johnson, 1989).

Cooperative learning is a structured small group arrangement in which students work together to achieve common objectives, and each student is responsible for their performance in the group as well as for the performance of the group as a whole (Jacobs & Hall, 2002; Jacobs et al., 2016). This approach has been shown in numerous studies to lead to improvements in social skills, communication, mutual respect, and civic involvement, as well as academic learning (Gillies, 2016). Theoretically, it is based on the Social Interdependence Theory, a generative condition for prosocial learning, which is positive interdependence and understanding that their success depends on others' success (Johnson & Johnson, 1989).

Despite this alignment, there have been very few empirical studies to explore the link between cooperative learning and citizenship education in Pakistan, especially from the lens of pre-service teachers. There is not much research on the Pakistani context that is based on existing studies of in-service teachers or quantitative measures of student achievement. Pre-service teachers have been under-researched as they are the next generation of classroom practitioners. This gap is significant as pre-service teachers bring with them conceptual schemes and pedagogic orientations acquired in their pre-service teacher experiences. Those orientations carry implications for sustainable implementation in Pakistani public schools if they cannot be enacted within the structural realities and limitations of these schools.

What are pre-service teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs about the concept of cooperative learning and citizenship education in Pakistan? What are their ideas about how teachers should relate cooperative learning to citizenship skills? What do they consider as obstacles and facilitating elements in implementing cooperative learning to teach citizenship at the elementary level? The purpose of this paper is to examine these questions and, in doing so, contribute to the field of pre-service teacher preparation, cooperative learning within South Asian contexts, as well as the structural conditions that impact pedagogical change in Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Interdependence Theory and Cooperative Learning

Johnson and Johnson (over several decades) (1989) have explored Social Interdependence Theory - that is, positive and negative interdependence - that is, positive interdependence means people cannot be successful without other people being successful; negative interdependence means people cannot be successful unless others fail. As cooperatively designed learning structures create positive interdependence, studies have shown that this results in prosocial behaviour of collaboration, communication, sharing decisions, and being held accountable by one's peers (Johnson et al., 2014). These are all skills that citizenship education aims to instil. Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory offers a complementary mechanism: the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) describes how scaffolding of more knowledgeable peers and teachers in their interactions with the student leads to the acquisition of knowledge the student is unable to learn on their own (Vygotsky, 1978). Cooperative learning has cognitive and civic scaffolding from both the teacher and a knowledgeable peer at the same time.

Citizenship Education: Frameworks and Pakistani Context

Westheimer and Kahne (2004) identify three types of citizens: a citizen who fulfils duties (called the "personally responsible" citizen), a citizen who is engaged in civic life (the "participatory" citizen), and a citizen who engages in structural challenges (the "justice-oriented" citizen). The citizenship education curriculum of Pakistan has always been focused on personal responsibility and the lack of investment in participatory and justice-oriented aspects of citizenship education (Dean, 2008; Muhammad & Brett, 2019). Biesta (2009) posits two opposing poles of citizenship education: one functionalist, inserting young people into existing social orders, and one emancipatory that has the potential to question existing social orders. This tension in Pakistan can be seen in the inability to move the curriculum from its desired to its real form, owing to the predominant transmission pedagogy in class teaching.

Cooperative Learning, Civic Competence, and Pre-Service Teacher Preparation

A review of recent decades of research shows that cooperative learning can be well structured to achieve substantial improvements in communication, empathy, and cooperative problem solving (Gillies, 2016). Slavin (2014) found that the cooperative learning model is superior to the conventional learning model in various cultural and academic success and social success.

In a South Asian context, it was discovered that cooperative learning sustained student engagement and civic participation even in the context of disruption in their COVID-19 schooling (Gopinathan et al., 2022; Hidayah et al., 2021). Despite these findings, Dayan et al. (2018) found that in the case of Pakistani pre-service teachers, only theoretical teaching and learning of the cooperative method occurs, which is not supported in practice. Chakyarkandiyil and Prakasha (2023) showed that as pre-service teachers in a similar context understood the importance of cooperative learning, their practical self-confidence is limited due to a lack of readiness. However, citizenship education can only be effective if teachers are structurally supported to implement it - something under-resourced school systems routinely fail to provide (Banks, 2004).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study followed a qualitative approach based on an interpretivist tradition. The research aimed to understand how participants make meaning of cooperative learning and citizenship education (Creswell & Poth, 2023), and a qualitative approach was appropriate. The analytic strategy chosen was Reflexive Thematic Analysis as it is flexible and suitable for analysis aimed at understanding the lived meaning of the participants rather than confirming with pre-existing categories (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The method is not discipline-specific and supports various epistemological stances (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Philosophical Paradigm

The study was conducted from an interpretivist/relativist ontological standpoint; that is, that reality is not fixed but constructed by the experiences and interactions of the participants. A social constructionist epistemological approach was used. Knowledge emerges through researcher-participant interaction in social and institutional fields. Language was not considered to be a literal window into the inner state of the participants but was seen as a way that the participants create and share their understandings. The orientation was largely constructivist, which gave space to the participants to think about what they thought and said and do what they saw, subject only to ongoing critical consideration of the structural conditions for this.

Analytic Approach

This analysis was largely inductive, meaning that codes and themes emerged from the data as opposed to being forced onto it from the theoretical approach. The meaning focus was semantic as well as latent, focused on both manifest content and latent meaning. This dual emphasis was appropriate for the study because its goal was to go beyond the content of the participants' discourse to discover how cooperative learning was implicitly related to citizenship formation.

Participants and Sampling

Ten participants were selected using a non-probability sampling technique with the method of purposive sampling (Patton, 2015). To be included in the study, candidates had to be in the 8th semester of BS Education from GC Women University, Sialkot, or have a minimum of one practicum in elementary schools and have studied the course material on citizenship (Creswell & Poth, 2023). The ten female pre-service teachers were representatives of the institutional context of the university. However, the researchers did not claim saturation (Malterud et al., 2016), but rather were able to estimate information power: the focused research question, the purposive sample, and the good quality data had sufficient information power for rigorous thematic analysis (Malterud et al., 2016).

Data Collection

Data were generated through semi-structured interviews addressing the research questions. Topics included the conceptualisation of cooperative learning, the relationship of cooperative learning with citizenship education, the perceived effectiveness of and strengths in cooperative learning, and hindering conditions in and facilitating conditions for cooperative learning. Interviews were conducted at the university and lasted 40-60 minutes and were audio-recorded with the participant's consent. All recordings were fully transcribed.

Data Analysis Procedures

Analysis was conducted in six phases of Reflexive TA (Braun & Clarke, 2022). During Phase 1, the researchers familiarised themselves with the data by repeated readings and made preliminary analytic notes. During Phase 2, codes were generated throughout the entire dataset based on explicit content and/or latent meanings. Codes were analysed for patterns and grouped into potential themes in Phase 3. Themes were reviewed and checked against the full dataset in Phase 4. During Phase 5, themes were refined and named to encapsulate the theme's central organising concept. In Phase 6, an analytic narrative was produced, which was rooted in the participant-quoted material.

Researcher Reflexivity

The researchers were BS Education students who had lived the teacher education system and practicum structure and had experienced institutional culture under study. This insider position facilitated analytic sensitivity; familiarity with the context helped researchers recognise structural elements, rather than them being background information. It also created a risk of confirmation bias. They kept these under control by having reflective journals: writing down any assumptions before the session of analysis and writing down which data were inconsistent with their assumptions.

Trustworthiness and Quality

Quality was evaluated based on criteria relevant to Big Q qualitative research: Whether findings aligned coherently with the research questions and method; the level of transparency of the applied method in making decisions about analysing data; whether interpretation moved beyond descriptive paraphrase; and whether the claims made were based on the specific data extracts. The researchers did not make use of inter-coder reliability, which is incompatible with the epistemological foundation that the themes are “constructed” and not “discovered.”

Ethical Considerations

Institutional approval for this study of the was obtained. The participants were informed and signed informed consent forms in which they were informed that they could withdraw without academic repercussions. Pseudonyms (Participant 01 to Participant 10) were used to anonymise the data. All recordings and transcripts were encrypted and password-protected, and only researchers had access to them.

4. FINDINGS

The relationship between conceptual constructions of cooperative learning, the teacher’s role, structural conditions experienced in practice, and the teacher’s perceptions about their professional readiness has been mapped as a result of this study into four themes.

Theme 1: Cooperative Learning as a Civic and Social Formation Process

Creating cooperative learning not merely as a way to run a group, but as a process of forming a social group where mutual civic dispositions are realised out of practice.

1a. Understanding Cooperative Learning Beyond Grouping

None of the ten subjects was satisfied with a definition of cooperative learning that meant students sitting in groups. They repeatedly stressed the interdependencies, shared responsibilities, and personal accountability. Participant 04 said: “Cooperative learning is work done in small groups with children, but it is not cooperative sitting, for example, one child sitting while another one is working, but rather working together and each child has a part. The difficulty lies in making sure that everyone has a part to play.” Participant 03 said, “It helps to acquire qualities in children that would not be acquired in another way, like getting together, talking about it, creating teams, and working together.” This was taken up by Participant ten who stated that cooperative learning “doesn’t just make children stronger in academics; it also makes children stronger socially.” Participants, therefore, created the method as an integrated academic and civic formation process in keeping with Social Interdependence Theory (Johnson & Johnson, 1989) as their way to experience the process.

1b. Civic Learning as Community Membership and Democratic Practice

Participants related specific classroom practices from their practicum experiences with respect to cooperative learning and democratic practice. Participant 04 explained an activity around voting.

I am writing them down in group form and asking them to vote for a number by using a group. There is no point in displaying anything. Everyone, please just raise their hands, and we will do fine. Whoever has the most votes wins! In cases of conflict, I have said to them that they should discuss their conflict and vote. These were the opportunities through which the children were able to learn about respecting other people’s views and to understand how to accept and comply with the majority opinion. This is a small level of democracy.

Participant 03 shared the following leadership election activity: “We teach leadership by group voting, so I ask for ideas and opinions from group members, and the candidates respect members’ ideas.” These examples show that participants did not view democratic participation as an abstract concept but had practised it in their classrooms and experienced its impact in civic terms.

Theme 2: The Indispensable Facilitative Role of the Teacher

Participants found that the success of constructing effective group work procedures for shaping civic potential in participants relied on the teacher’s active, structured, and sustained facilitation.

2a. Role Assignment as Pedagogical and Civic Practice

Role assignment was seen as a “bedrock” element by all participants. Participant 06 spoke about using a student as the leader, one as the presenter, and one as the writer. Participant 03 stated that the civic nature is that “the leader’s role is to assign and distribute work, offer instructions to members, and treat everyone fairly when the teacher assigns group work.” Thus, role assignment was designed not just as a classroom management strategy but as a classroom space for learning citizenship, for exercising responsibility and equity structurally.

2b. Monitoring, Reinforcement, and Inclusion of Reluctant Learners

Participant 03 reported, “The work does not get done if the teacher is not actively working with the group. Students who were reluctant/underconfident were also treated.” Participant 03 explained how she supported her shy and less confident student: “If I had a shy and less confident student here in my classroom, then I support him/her and perhaps make him a group leader, but they learn a lot from him/her, and they become confident.” Participant 04 mentioned the affective aspect as follows: “What I really enjoy about my practice is when a student who is insecure about herself gives a presentation that she is confident about.” The teaching role was located in the notion of a pedagogically and civically generative role.

Theme 3: Systemic Barriers to Implementation in Pakistani Public School Settings

Participants framed the main barriers to cooperative learning in a primarily structural and systemic way rather than a pedagogical and attitudinal way.

3a. Resource Deficits and Physical Infrastructure

Participant 01 explained why some problems were experienced in her practicum experience: “I went to a public school where I implemented cooperative learning, but there are numerous difficulties, such as public schools having some materials, instruction mostly uses blackboards, internet facilities for students are low, and whiteboards or projectors also cannot be found.” Participant 04 observed: “Classroom space is a major concern – There are 40+ students in a small classroom – Group division is difficult under these circumstances.” These descriptions demonstrate situations in student learning that were felt not merely inconvenient, but systemic in nature, which limited cooperative learning in its actualisation in the learning as participants had envisioned it.

3b. Institutional Culture, Examination Pressure, and Community Scepticism

Participant 03 pointed out the importance of teacher training: “Otherwise, there are problems in the schools for the cooperative learning implementation.” Participant 08 correlated resource inadequacies with an emphasis on teacher priorities on examination outcomes, as opposed to promoting active learning. Parent scepticism was expressed by Participant 04: “Some parents do not know what cooperative learning is; they think that the students are only playing or wasting their time.” Participant 09 said that the students were not accustomed to cooperative learning or working together because they had been trained in the transmission teaching process. Such accounts show an interplay of examination, institutional leadership, parental regulations, and learner acculturation towards a transmission orientation of the classroom.

Theme 4: Conditional Readiness and the Practicum Design Gap

Participants constructed their professional readiness in partial and conditional terms, with success depending on their practicum experiences. However, they did not feel completely ready due to the short duration of their placements, which meant that there was not sufficient scope for them to complete the cycle needed for cooperative learning competence.

4a. Practicum as the Primary Source of Professional Confidence

Professional confidence for all participants was found during the practicum experience, not through coursework on campus. Participant 02 reported that she was confident in putting cooperative learning into practice “because she had implemented it during teaching practice.” Participant 03 agreed: “I got a lot from their teaching practice, as well as things from their skilled teachers. Work-based learning was found to be the most legitimising context for the profession.”

4b. Short Placements and Incomplete Professional Development

All participants who spoke directly about the duration of placement indicated that it was lacking, although for some, it was a positive component of practicum. According to Participant 01, she had tried the cooperative learning method during the 15-day teaching practice, but this experience was too short; she needed more experience. Participant 04 explained the process of building competencies, which is: “When I tried cooperative learning the first time, it was hard, the second time it was okay, and the third time it was effective. But I need more experience.”

Some of the participants assessed their readiness at 60–70%. This self-evaluation was consistent with the structural evaluation they gave during other parts of their interviews.

DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Findings

The four themes form a coherent argument. Cooperative learning is a modality of civic formation that participants understand; they understand the conditions necessary for cooperative learning to be facilitative; they have experienced what gets in the way of cooperative learning; and they can see the gap between what they are currently able to do and what the job requires. This is not a portrait of an undriven or unaware teacher; it is a portrait of a structurally constrained teacher. The primary finding from the study is that the issue of cooperative learning in the context of citizenship education in Pakistan is mainly structural, which is related to the fact that practicum placements are of limited duration, the condition of public schools, and the lack of continuous mentored support.

Connection to Existing Literature

Teacher facilitation is, in this study, the most important single element of the effectiveness of cooperative learning, as Gillies (2016) has found, and so we think our participants might have thought. This confirms that the link between cooperative learning and citizenship development is practical for teachers who have implemented it. The results expand on Westheimer and Kahne (2004) in one particular respect: The descriptions provided by participants showed that for this group, the most salient aspects of citizenship are personally responsible and participatory citizenship, while justice-oriented citizenship is less developed. This is in the context of the developmental environment, where children are in elementary school, and the emphasis of the curriculum in Pakistan is on citizenship education. This study gives voice to pre-service teachers and presents a rich qualitative account of the experience of the theory-practice gap in pre-service teacher education in Pakistan as a persistent structural condition. Although not surprising, it was a known obstacle that the participants were not trained to overcome.

Implications

The theoretical implications indicate that pre-service teachers develop an understanding of cooperative learning that is grounded in their experiences and is complex without any teaching about Social Interdependence Theory or Vygotskian scaffolding. Teacher education design should build on this foundation. Practicum design is the most immediate implication, as currently, there is no time to experience the multiple steps in the experiential cycle that current

practitioners perceive as essential for competence in their professional development. Placements should be for a minimum of six weeks, which must be continuous, and cooperative learning mentorship cycles should be integrated into the placement. At the policy level, it is recommended that the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan bring changes in the Programme Standards of BS Education so that these extended placements may be stipulated, and cooperative learning competency indicators should be integrated into the School Inspection System.

Limitations

The study was conducted in one institution consisting of ten pre-service female teachers. The findings are not statistically generalisable but may be analytically transferred to settings that have similar institutional and structural characteristics. Data rely on retrospective self-reports from participants and reflect the retrospection of the participants; data are drawn from a single source.

Future Research Directions

In the future, investigating whether cooperative learning competencies transfer in Pakistani public schools is needed by undertaking longitudinal studies of pre-service teachers after implementation. Research on student outcomes should examine whether cooperative learning measurably fosters civic competencies in elementary students, as this study generated only process data. To understand implementation, comparative studies between the context of government and private schools would shed some light.

CONCLUSION

The present study explored the ways in which pre-service teachers at a Pakistani university constructed cooperative learning as a vehicle for teaching citizenship education in elementary school. Semi-structured interviews with ten final-year BS Education students were conducted and used to generate four themes using Reflexive Thematic Analysis. The first theme revealed how participants constructed cooperative learning as a space of social and civic formation, where structured interdependence and democratic practice develop civic competence. The second theme showed that participants built the need for active teacher facilitation, that is, active facilitation, including role assignment, monitoring, and inclusion, as necessary conditions for civic potential. The third theme indicated that systemic issues such as resource shortages, excessive class sizes, stress with exams, and systemic barriers constrain

implementation beyond any individual teacher's capacity. The fourth theme defined that participants' professional readiness is contingent, although it is grounded in practicum experience; short placements restricted development and prevented the iterative development of cooperative learning competence.

The major finding of this study is the problem of implementing cooperative learning for citizenship education as structural, not only pedagogic. Cooperative learning is a means of developing citizenship, and pre-service teachers are provided with conceptual resources and civic motivation to do so. They lack extended placements, mentored partnerships, resourced classrooms, and cultures that value learning processes. Teacher education reform is necessary but not sufficient for change at the school and policy levels. For curriculum designers and policy makers, the implications are clear: Realising the civic potential of cooperative learning requires structural and curricular change.

Future research should examine these constructions when pre-service teachers become full-time teachers. The gap between vision and structure identified here, which is unlikely to be addressed at the level of qualification, is likely to deepen within the realities of public school life in Pakistan, as newly qualified teachers encounter those realities. Longitudinal and outcome studies are needed to determine conditions for scaling and under which cooperative learning for citizenship can be sustained.

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